

Editorial

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EASE statement on continued importance of sex and gender equity in research (SAGER)

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Since President Trump's inauguration on 20 January 2025, the White House has issued multiple Executive Orders affecting scientific researchers in the USA and globally.¹ Some of these Executive Orders specifically address the publication of important demographic data and the language to be used when reporting scientific findings, in contradiction to established best scientific practices.

On behalf of The European Association of Science Editors (EASE), we would like to reaffirm the editorial responsibility of scholarly journals to uphold the integrity of the scientific record and the core principles of the scientific community. Editors and journals should adhere to established scientific consensus and evidence-based practices, ensuring that their activities and processes align with the highest standards of ethical and academic rigor.

While there is still some uncertainty in the academic debate regarding the exact definitions of sex and gender, there is a consensus that the variables describing sex and gender are key features of research design, contributing to the validity and applicability of research findings, as defined in the Sex and Gender Equity in Research (SAGER) guidelines.² Implementing the SAGER guidelines³ enhances transparency and reproducibility, contributing to equitable and effective health interventions and policies.⁴ Failure to fully account for sex and gender dimensions in biomedical, health, and care research leads to gaps in the evidence base, which translates into worse clinical outcomes for all people.^{5,6} Sex and gender analysis also has the potential to foster scientific discovery, improve experimental efficiency, and enable social equality across a wide range of scientific and engineering disciplines.⁷

The existence of homosexual, transgender, transsexual, and other identities is a scientific

fact, recognized as normal human variation,⁸ not a faith-based or political concept. The EASE strongly recommends the collection and reporting of accurate data, according to the SAGER guidelines,² to maintain the integrity of the science. EASE also recommends the use of respectful, inclusive language in all scientific publications.

Some US-based researchers might consider that they are unable to be listed as authors of papers on certain topics, including gender diversity, due to possible retaliation. The International Committee of Medical Journal Editors has issued guidance⁹ on how journals could show flexibility in response to requests to withdraw, revise, or alter authorship of manuscripts. Similarly, we encourage editors to work with authors, as necessary, to enable them to meet current political requirements, for example regarding language concerning sex and gender, within the framework of best editorial practices in scholarly publishing.

We acknowledge that this is a difficult time for authors, researchers, and editors in the USA; however, the principles of research integrity, transparency, and human rights should not be subject to political agendas.

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